

THE ROLE OF HOME READING IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN A GENERAL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION

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Annotation

This article reveals about the role of home reading in the process of teaching English and shows importance of reading as well as the types of reading and their implementation in educational organization. In the article, analytical, synthetic, transferable, untranslatable types of reading are widely explained. Moreover, the importance of reading is proven with its practical values. Therefore, researchers, students and English teachers can get much valuable information in this article.

Key words: reading, technique, cognitive, introductory reading, value-oriented

In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, reading is an independent type of speech activity that provides a written form of communication, and also occupies one of the main places in terms of use, importance and accessibility.

In the process of teaching foreign languages, reading performs two functions:

Reading is the goal of learning, i.e. is a type of speech activity (a means of extracting information);

Reading is a means of teaching other types of speech activity¹.

Currently, reading is considered as a process of perception and active processing of information graphically encoded according to the system of a particular language and is a complex analytical and synthetic activity that consists of the perception and understanding of the text, and the most perfect (mature) reading is characterized by the fusion of these two processes and focus on the semantic side of the content.

To read in a foreign language means to exercise a complex speech skill in order to obtain new information contained in a graphic source representing it, called a text, and coming through the visual channel².

Successful implementation of reading comprehension is possible if there are a number of factors that ensure this process:

1. Possession of certain language material.

2. The presence of certain skills and abilities, an indispensable condition for the functioning of which is the participation of categories of a psychological order: attention, different types of memory, logical thinking, etc.

In this regard, the role of speech hearing in the process of reading is extremely important. It is determined by the peculiarity of the sound-letter system of printed text. First,

¹ Гурвич П.Б. Обучение неподготовленной речи // Иностранные языки в школе. - 1964. - №1. - С. 54.

² Гез Н.И., Ляховицкий М.В., Миролубов А.А. и др. Методика обучения иностранным языкам в средней школе // М.: Высшая школа, 1982. - 125 с.

display. I.L.Bim marks, that display is addressed to sensual perception of pupils - acoustical, visual, motor³. The teacher can accompany display by some explanatory;

Probabilistic forecasting ("mental overtaking in the process of reading") also acts as an integral component of active mental activity and determines the success of perception and understanding in any kind of reading. Forecasting helps to create in students an emotional attitude, readiness for reading. Depending on students' prior experiences, related cases and scaffolding may be necessary for support. Instructors also need to provide an authentic context for tasks, plus information resources, cognitive tools, and collaborative tools⁴.

In the process of reading, the reader needs to perform such mental operations as comparison and generalization, analysis and synthesis, abstraction and concretization, establishment of cause-and-effect relationships, etc.

According to G.V. Horny, the reading process itself can be divided into the following components:

- 1) correlation of graphemes with morphemes;
- 2) the formation of holistic methods of recognition of graphic signs;
- 3) the formation of internal speech hearing;

4) inward translation of external pronunciation and the establishment of a direct connection between the semantic and graphic complexes, which finds its expression in reading aloud and silently, slow and fast, with full understanding or general coverage⁵.

It is known from psychology that mastering reading begins with the perception of the printed word, its voicing and understanding, i.e. from mastering grapheme-morpheme correspondences in a foreign language. This is also the case for reading phrases, sentences and text. Reading is not only the perception of the text being read, but also its understanding. In real reading, the processes of perception and understanding are closely interrelated. The skills that provide these processes are usually divided into two groups:

a) technical reading skills (they provide perceptual processing of the text: the perception of graphic signs and their correlation with certain meanings or the recoding of visual signals into semantic units);

b) skills and abilities of semantic processing of perceived information (these skills lead to the understanding of the text as a complete speech statement).

Knowledge of sound-letter correspondences and the ability to predict the development of language material are among the main mechanisms of reading technique. Teaching reading techniques should be carried out in parallel with teaching other types of speech activity.

It is known that the reading technique is not a sufficient condition for understanding the text and the relationship between technical skills and understanding is not straightforward, which practically means the possibility of understanding with an insufficiently developed reading technique and, conversely, the possibility of achieving a certain level in reading technique with a rather superficial understanding. However, a large

³ Bim I.L. Possible forms and content of foreign language courses in elementary school. // Foreign languages at school. - 2001. - No. 2. - p. 3.

⁴ Jonassen D.H. Constructing learning environments on the web: Engaging students in meaningful learning. EdTech 99: Educational Technology Conference and Exhibition 1999: Thinking Schools, Learning Nation. - 1999 - p. 45-46

⁵ Рогова Г.В. и др. Методика обучения иностранным языкам в средней школе. - М.: Просвещение, 1991. -- 87 с.

gap between the technical and semantic sides of reading is impossible, and the main place in this unity belongs to understanding.

As giving outcome we can mention some features that are unique to reading should be noted. Reading comprehension is carried out under somewhat more favorable conditions, which are determined by the greater clarity of visual images compared to auditory ones and the longer duration of their impact. At the same time, the content of the material during reading is, as a rule, more difficult. The subject of oral speech usually covers subjects close to the speaker, directly related to him. When reading, the range of questions is much wider, especially at the middle and senior stages of learning a foreign language. For texts borrowed from the popular science, political and fiction of the country of the language being studied, it is typical, in particular, to refer to topics that reflect the life and history of this country, which leads to an acquaintance with facts and objects that are not in the experience of the reader.

Types of reading in the methodology of teaching foreign languages

The main purpose of reading is to comprehend visually perceived information and understand it. Reading a person is always purposeful, depending on the specific goal at a particular moment of reading.

In the methodological literature, it is customary to distinguish three types of reading: cognitive, value-oriented and regulatory.

THE FUNCTION OF READING

- cognitive** - reading on information, comprehend and store it, briefly react to it, verbally or in writing.
- value-oriented** - read to evaluate, retell the content of what was read, i.e. use the results of reading in other activities.
- regulatory** - reading with subsequent substantive actions that correlate or do not correlate with those described in the text.

Regulatory - reading with subsequent substantive actions that correlate or do not correlate with those described in the text.

Depending on the degree of participation of the voice, the types of reading are divided into reading:

- 1) out loud;
- 2) choral (as a kind of reading aloud);
- 3) about yourself.

Reading aloud - external sounding of graphic text. The ratio of reading aloud and reading to oneself varies depending on the purpose of the lesson and the stage of learning. Reading aloud is especially important at the initial stage during the formation of auditory pronunciation and rhythmic intonation skills and mastering the technique of reading⁶.

Choral (polyphonic) reading - simultaneous reading by the class of a passage of a pre-selected text. This technique is used in lessons in a number of subjects, and it gives good results, provided that the teacher has a developed ear and distributed attention, thanks to which he hears individual voices in the choir and corrects the mistakes made by the students. Choral exercises have a positive effect on correcting a number of shortcomings in speech (patter, loudness, lethargy, etc.)⁷.

⁶ Азимов Э.Г., Шукин А.Н. Новый словарь методических терминов (теория и практика обучения языкам). - М.: Издательство «ИКАР», 2009. - 347 с.

⁷ Азимов Э.Г., Шукин А.Н. Новый словарь методических терминов (теория и практика обучения языкам). - М.: Издательство «ИКАР», 2009. - 254 с.

Silent reading is the process of reading without speaking the words aloud. Teaching this type of reading is of great importance. Introduction to reading to oneself begins already at the initial stage, being a subordinate form of reading aloud. Sometimes it is used as a certain stage of learning to read aloud, when the processes of perception and understanding have not yet become simultaneous; students run through the text with their eyes, grasping its general content, looking for an adequate intonation. Then reading to oneself begins to “break through” as an independent activity, first in a small volume, and then expanding from class to class.

According to the method of disclosure of content, reading can be divided into:

- analytical;
- synthetic;
- transferable;
- untranslatable (with direct understanding).

Analytical reading is reading deeper than with the reproductive perception of the text, reflecting only the development of the topic, the presence of concepts and ideas. This is a cross-reading, comparing new information with previously received information, comparing different positions of the author among themselves, this is reading with the development of one's own assessment and attitudes to what has been read, reflecting one's own experience through what has been read, this is the identification of hidden meanings of the text. Such reading, as a rule, takes notes, uses dictionaries, reads at a reasonable pace, revisiting what has been read, etc.

This is always meaningful reading, accompanied by the transformation of someone else's text into one's personal attitude and knowledge.

Synthetic reading is an educational type of reading according to the method of disclosing the content, taking into account the psychological setting for fast reading. This type of reading is built on the basis of a strong command of lexical and grammatical material, the ability to recognize the meaning of unknown words by context and formal features, the semantics of word-forming elements and the function of words in a sentence, as well as the ability to construct a whole according to separately perceived parts.

Translation reading - develops the ability to independently work on a foreign text and use dictionaries and reference books. However, the abundant use of translation hinders the formation of a direct, intuitive, holistic understanding of the content of the text.

Reading without translation is a type of reading without the participation of the native language in understanding what is being read. It is characterized by a significant predominance of intuitive perception of a foreign text and a direct understanding of the content⁸.

Also, according to the venue, the reading is divided into:

- a) home;
- b) cool.

Home reading is mandatory for all students, additional to the textbook, constant and abundant reading in order to extract meaningful information. This is extracurricular reading. According to the method of reading, this is reading to oneself or in an ideal form - visual reading, as the most perfect and mature reading.

⁸ Беспальчикова. Е.В. Обучение анализу текста // Иностранные языки в школе. - 2002. - № 2. - С. 28.

Classroom reading is a form of organizing educational work at the venue. This type is organized by the teacher in the classroom (in the classroom).

By the nature of the organization of activities:

- ✓ prepared;
- ✓ unprepared.

Prepared reading involves removing language difficulties before reading the text.

Unprepared reading is carried out on language-friendly, adapted texts⁹.

In the process of teaching foreign languages, the classification of types of reading is widely used depending on the target setting, proposed by S. Kh. Folomkina¹⁰, who divides educational reading into the following types, which are also defined as program types of reading:

- ✓ viewing;
- ✓ fact-finding;
- ✓ studying;
- ✓ search.

Viewing reading involves obtaining a general idea of the material being read. Its purpose is to obtain the most general idea of the topic and range of issues addressed in the text. Such reading takes place during the initial acquaintance with the content of a new publication in order to determine whether it contains information of interest to the reader, and on this basis to decide whether to read it or not. It can also end with the presentation of the results of what has been read in the form of a message or abstract. To teach viewing reading, it is necessary to select a number of thematically related text materials and create viewing situations. The speed of viewing reading should not be lower than 500 words per minute, and learning tasks should be aimed at developing skills and abilities to navigate the logical and semantic structure of the text, the ability to extract and use the material of the source text in accordance with a specific communicative task.

Introductory reading is a cognitive reading, in which the entire speech work (book, article, story) becomes the subject of the reader's attention without setting to receive specific information. This is reading "for oneself", without prior special installation for the subsequent use or reproduction of the information received. The main communicative task facing the reader is to quickly read the entire text to extract the basic information contained in it, i.e. find out what issues and how are resolved in the text, what exactly it says on these issues. The pace of introductory reading should not be less than 180 words per minute. For practice in this type of reading, relatively long texts are used, which are easy in terms of language, containing at least 25 - 30% of redundant, secondary information.

Study reading provides for the most complete and accurate understanding of all the information contained in the text and its critical comprehension. The object of "study" in this type of reading is the information contained in the text. Its task is also to develop the student's ability to independently overcome difficulties in understanding a foreign text. The pace of studying reading is 50 - 60 words per minute. For this type of reading, texts are selected that

⁹ Калистра. И. Д. Чтение с предварительно снятыми трудностями понимания // Вопросы обучению устной речи и чтению на иностранном языке. - 2003. - № 4. -- С. 23-28.

¹⁰ Фоломкина С. К. Некоторые вопросы обучения чтению на иностранном языке в неязыковом вузе. Методика и психология обучения иностранным языкам: хрестоматия / сост. Леонтьев А. А. - М.: НИУ ВШЭ, 2010. - 483 с

have cognitive value, informative significance and present the greatest difficulty for this stage of learning, both in terms of content and language.

Search reading is focused on reading newspapers and literature in the specialty. Its goal is to quickly find quite specific data in the text (facts, characteristics, numerical indicators, etc.). In educational conditions, search reading acts more like an exercise, since the search for this or that information, as a rule, is carried out at the direction of the teacher. Therefore, it is usually an accompanying component in the development of other types of reading¹¹. The principle of selecting content for teaching reading at school should be the inclusion of all its types. The main sign of achieving a high level of development of reading skills is the ability of the student to change the nature of the activity depending on the specific situation, the purpose of reading. The reader must have the ability to switch from one type of reading to another, taking into account the specific task that he sets for himself.

The task of the text period of reading aloud is to lead students to the simultaneous perception and understanding of the text. At the same time, the development and improvement of perception is carried out in unity with the solution of semantic tasks.

It should be noted that the reader already at the initial stage should:

- know the names of letters and correlate letters with the sounds they transmit; correctly pronounce an unfamiliar word in an isolated position and in a sentence;
- Match the word with the meaning
- Recognize famous words in an unfamiliar text;
- Navigate the structure of the text (find headings, the beginning and end of a paragraph, captions under figures, etc.);
- Recognize the types of text (verse, rhyme, story, dialogue, crossword puzzle, comics, etc.);
- Rely on the rules of spelling;
- Read aloud expressively and correctly;
- Determine the meaning of new words by word formation and context;
- Overcome the focus on articulation¹².

The skills listed above are designed to provide the conditions for the flow of reading as a form of verbal communication, that is, to create a perceptual-semantic basis for perception and teach students to operate with language material in the amount of sentences, semantic pieces and simple texts.

When reading with a selective understanding of the necessary or interesting information, the ability to review a text or several short texts and select information that is necessary or of particular interest is formed¹³.

Conclusions: reading is an independent type of speech activity that provides a written form of communication. Successful implementation of reading comprehension is possible with the possession of certain language material and with the presence of certain skills and abilities. There are technical reading skills and skills of semantic processing of perceived information.

In the methodological literature, it is customary to classify the types of reading: according to the function of reading, depending on the degree of participation of the voice,

¹¹ Фадеев. В.М. Домашнее чтение в старших классах, его организация и способы контроля // Иностранные языки в школе. - 1979.- № 6. - С. 30.

¹² Коньшева А.В. Контроль результатов обучения иностранному языку - СПб., 2004. - 135 с.

¹³ Коньшева А.В. Контроль результатов обучения иностранному языку - СПб., 2004. – 64 с.

according to the method of disclosing the content, according to the venue, depending on the target setting (programmatic types of reading).

The final level of a school graduate's learning in the field of reading is achieved gradually and is improved at each stage of education. The ultimate goal of school teaching to read is the ability to read authentic texts of various styles and genres, using the main types of reading, depending on the communicative task.

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